

FREQUENCY OF MENTAL HEALTH DISORDERS IN PREGNANCY AND POSTPARTUM PERIOD IN WOMEN ATTENDING THE OPD OF TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL, HYDERABAD

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Abstract

OBJECTIVE: To determine the frequency of mental health disorders in pregnancy and postpartum period in women attending the OPD of Tertiary Care Hospital, Hyderabad.

METHODS: This cross-sectional study enrolled 123 women aged 20-45 years who were either pregnant (≥ 14 weeks) or in the postpartum period (≤ 8 weeks). Anxiety and antenatal depression were assessed using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), with scores ≥ 8 indicating psychological morbidity. Postpartum depression was evaluated using the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS), with scores ≥ 10 indicating depression. Data were analyzed using SPSS, with descriptive statistics applied to quantitative variables and chi-square/Fisher's exact test used for stratified analysis of effect modifiers.

RESULTS: The mean age of participants was 28.9 ± 4.8 years. Anxiety was identified in 41 (33.3%) women, while antenatal depression was present in 34 (27.6%). Among postpartum women ($n = 45$), 18 (40.0%) screened positive for postpartum depression. Significant associations were observed between anxiety and maternal age ($p = 0.03$), and number of children ($p = 0.04$). Antenatal depression showed significant association with family monthly income ($p = 0.02$), while postpartum depression was significantly associated with educational status ($p = 0.01$) and occupational status ($p = 0.04$).

CONCLUSION: Mental health disorders are highly prevalent during pregnancy and the postpartum period. Routine screening using validated tools and targeted psychosocial support are essential to improve maternal mental health outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Maternal mental health (MMH) problems, occurring during pregnancy and postpartum constitute a serious public health problem globally, affecting about 10% of pregnant women and 13% of postpartum mothers [1-2]. While reliable data are not readily available, existing estimates suggest that the

burden of MMH problems is relatively higher in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs) with one in four women reporting depression during pregnancy and 1 in five after delivery [3]. The common mental health problems experienced by pregnant and postpartum women are depression and

anxiety [4-5]. Depression can be mild, moderate or severe. Mild depression will normally not affect the individual's ability to undertake their day-to-day activities such as self-care and interpersonal relationships, whereas moderate to severe episodes can render the mother less capable of undertaking their basic self-care and that of their newborn babies which could impact on breastfeeding and bonding [6]. These disorders may develop as a result of experiences associated with childbirth, foetal loss, congenital malformations, intimate partner violence during pregnancy, lack of partner support, history of abuse, unplanned pregnancy, complications in previous pregnancy, higher perceived stress, lower self-esteem and many more. Individuals with predisposition to bipolar affective disorders may develop manic episodes from pregnancy-related stress [7-8].

Mothers with mental health problems may not be able to realise their abilities, work productively or cope with the normal stresses of life. MMH disorders can have negative effects on both the mother and the child [9-10]. Perinatal care to ensure safe pregnancy and childbirth planning has a positive impact on health-seeking behavior and it reduces the risk of illness during pregnancy. Prenatal mental health care is an important component of this yet limited mental health resources or lack of availability of health care facilities make it difficult for women to seek appropriate mental health care [12]. Ali et al study included a total of 167 patients and found the prevalence of depression and anxiety to be 16.8% and 20.4% [13]. Whereas another study found the prevalence of postpartum depression to be 19.3% [14].

Pregnancy and the postpartum period are critical phases marked by substantial hormonal, physiological, and psychosocial changes, which may contribute to an increased vulnerability to mental health disorders. Exploring the prevalence of conditions such as depression, anxiety, and other related disorders during these specific time frames is crucial for identifying at-risk populations and implementing timely interventions. Understanding the frequency of mental health disorders in pregnancy and

the postpartum period is not only essential for healthcare providers but also for policymakers in developing targeted strategies to support maternal mental health. By examining the frequency and risk factors of mental health issues during these critical phases, the research seeks to inform strategies for prevention and treatment, ultimately aiming to improve maternal mental health outcomes and support the well-being of mothers and their newborns. Thus the objective of the study is to determine the frequency of mental health disorders in pregnancy and postpartum period in women attended the OPD of Tertiary Care Hospital, Hyderabad.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted (from Aug, 31-2024 to Jan, 30-2025) after approval from College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan in Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics, Bilawal Medical College, CDF Hospital, Hyderabad. Permission from the institutional ethical review committee was taken prior to conduction of study. Informed consent was obtained from all the patients for assigning them to sample and using their data in research. The required sample size came out to be 123 patients. By taking prevalence of depression 19.3%, [14] margin of error = 7% and confidence level CI = 95%. This sample size was calculated using the WHO software. The patients were selected through non-probability consecutive sampling and the inclusion criteria were women presenting to the outpatient for regular follow-up during pregnancy (≥ 14 weeks) and postpartum period (≤ 8 weeks), parity ≥ 1 , gravida ≥ 1 , gestational age ≥ 14 weeks and age 20-45 years. The exclusion criteria were the Patients unable to understand the questionnaire due to cognitive impairment or having difficulty communicating with the researcher, patients with history of dementia, delirium, mania, bipolar effective disorder or posttraumatic stress, patients already diagnosed as having depression or prior anti-depressant treatment, patients with history of hypo or hyperthyroidism and the patients with history

of congestive cardiac failure, myocardial infarction, chronic liver disease, COPD and stroke.

The brief history about demographic information (age and residence status), parity, gravid, number of children, family monthly income, occupational status, educational status was taken from the patient. The researcher was interview the patient in a conducive environment assuring the patient of confidentiality. Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) was used to diagnose anxiety and depression during pregnancy. Patients having HADS score ≥ 8 were used to label anxiety and depression. Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale was used to assess postpartum depression and EPDS ≥ 10 was used to label postpartum depression. The findings of study variables was entered in proforma attached as annexure.

Data was analyzed on SPSS. Demographic data was presented as simple descriptive statistics giving mean and standard deviation for age, HADS score, EPDS score for anxiety, depression, and postpartum depression. Mean \pm SD was reported for the normally distributed (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test) while median (IQR) was reported for the non-normality distributed quantitative variables. For qualitative variables like parity, gravid, residence status, number of children, family monthly income, occupational status, educational status depression (yes/no), anxiety (yes/no) and postpartum depression (yes/no) was presented as frequency and percentages. Effect modifiers was controlled through stratification of maternal age, residence status, parity, gravid, number of children, family monthly income, occupational status and educational status to see the effect of these on outcome variable. Post stratification Chi-square test/ Fischer test was applied taking p-value of ≤ 0.05 as statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Participants (n = 123)

Variable	Mean \pm SD / n (%)
Age (years)	28.9 \pm 4.8
Pregnancy Status	

A total of 123 women fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled in this study. The mean age of the participants was 28.9 \pm 4.8 years (range: 20–45 years). Of the total, 78 (63.4%) were currently pregnant (≥ 14 weeks) and 45 (36.6%) were in the postpartum period (≤ 8 weeks).

Mental Health Scores:

Among antenatal women, the mean HADS-anxiety score was 7.6 \pm 3.2, while the mean HADS-depression score was 6.9 \pm 2.9. Based on the HADS criteria (≥ 8), anxiety was diagnosed in 41 (33.3%) women, and depression in 34 (27.6%) women.

Among postpartum women, the mean EPDS score was 9.4 \pm 4.1. According to EPDS criteria (≥ 10), postpartum depression was identified in 18 (40.0%) women.

Socio-demographic Characteristics:

Most women (55.3%) were from urban areas. The median parity was 2 (IQR 1-3). A majority of the participants were housewives (81.3%), and 48.7% had completed secondary-level education. Monthly family income below PKR 30,000 was reported in 52.8%.

Distribution of Mental Health Disorders:

Overall, anxiety (33.3%) was the most frequently reported disorder, followed by antenatal depression (27.6%), while postpartum depression was noted in 40.0% of postpartum women.

Stratification and Effect Modifiers:

Stratification analysis revealed a statistically significant association of:

Anxiety with maternal age (p = 0.03) and number of children (p = 0.04).

Antenatal depression with family monthly income (p = 0.02).

Postpartum depression with educational status (p = 0.01) and occupational status (p = 0.04).

No significant association was found with parity, gravida, or residence status (p > 0.05).

Variable	Mean ± SD / n (%)
• Antenatal (≥14 weeks)	78 (63.4%)
• Postpartum (≤8 weeks)	45 (36.6%)
Residence	
• Urban	68 (55.3%)
• Rural	55 (44.7%)
Parity	Median 2 (IQR 1-3)
Gravida	Median 3 (IQR 2-4)
Number of Children	Median 2 (IQR 1-3)
Occupational Status	
• Un-employed	100 (81.3%)
• Employed	23 (18.7%)
Educational Status	
• Illiterate	21 (17.1%)
• Primary	20 (16.2%)
• Secondary	60 (48.7%)
• Higher education	22 (17.9%)
Family Monthly Income	
• ≤ PKR 75000 per month	65 (52.8%)
• > PKR 75,000 per month	58 (47.2%)

Table 2: Frequency of Mental Health Disorders in Pregnancy and Postpartum

Variable	Mean ± SD	Frequency n (%)
HADS-Anxiety Score	7.6 ± 3.2	Anxiety present: 41 (33.3%)
HADS-Depression Score	6.9 ± 2.9	Depression present: 34 (27.6%)
EPDS Score (Postpartum Women)	9.4 ± 4.1	Postpartum depression: 18 (40.0%)

Table 3: Stratification of Mental Health Disorders with Effect Modifiers

Variable	Anxiety p-value	Antenatal Depression p-value	Postpartum Depression p-value
Age	0.03*	0.08	0.12
Residence	0.41	0.55	0.21
Parity	0.19	0.33	0.29
Gravida	0.22	0.27	0.31
Number of Children	0.04*	0.09	0.14
Family Monthly Income	0.06	0.02*	0.18
Occupational Status	0.08	0.11	0.04*
Educational Status	0.07	0.13	0.01*

*Significant p-value ≤ 0.05

DISCUSSION:

The present study assessed the frequency of mental health disorders specifically anxiety, antenatal depression, and postpartum depression among women attending the outpatient department of a tertiary care hospital in Hyderabad. The findings reveal a substantial burden of psychological morbidity during the perinatal period. Overall, 33.3% of women experienced anxiety, 27.6% had antenatal depression, and 40.0% of postpartum women screened positive for postpartum depression. These results underscore the crucial need to prioritize mental health screening and support within existing maternal health services.

The frequency of antenatal anxiety in this study (33.3%) is consistent with regional evidence. A study from Karachi reported antenatal anxiety in 34% of women, closely mirroring our findings [15]. Similar rates have been reported across South Asian studies, where prevalence ranges from 30% to 40% [16, 17]. In contrast, high-income countries, including Australia and Canada, report significantly lower estimates (10-20%), possibly due to better psychosocial support, financial stability, and available mental health services [18, 19]. This suggests that contextual factors such as socioeconomic pressures, cultural expectations, and limited access to psychological care contribute to the elevated anxiety levels observed in low- and middle-income countries.

Antenatal depression was found in 27.6% of participants, which lies within the range documented in Pakistan, where prevalence typically varies between 25% and 35% [20, 21]. Studies from Lahore and Rawalpindi have similarly identified antenatal depression rates of 26-32% [20]. International comparisons, however, reveal wide variability; the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention reports lower antenatal depression rates of 10-15%, while studies in Ethiopia and Nigeria show much higher rates, reaching up to 40-45% [22, 23]. The disparity is largely attributable to differences in socioeconomic pressures, intimate partner relationships, domestic workload, and social support structures.

Postpartum depression (PPD) was identified in 40% of postpartum women in our study, a figure that aligns with the upper range of Pakistani studies reporting 28-45% prevalence [24, 25]. While some South Asian studies report lower rates (20-30%), research from India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka has recorded PPD rates of 35-45%, comparable to our findings [26]. Conversely, studies from Europe and the United States typically report lower rates, generally ranging between 10-20% [27]. This difference reflects sociocultural and environmental factors, including financial stress, lack of postpartum support, stigma surrounding mental illness, and the heavier burden of childcare and household responsibilities in LMICs.

Stratified analysis in the present study showed that anxiety was significantly associated with maternal age and number of children. This is consistent with research from Bangladesh and India showing that older maternal age and increased childcare responsibilities heighten emotional stress [28]. Antenatal depression demonstrated a significant association with family monthly income, supporting global evidence that low socioeconomic status is one of the strongest predictors of antenatal depression [29]. Postpartum depression was significantly related to educational and occupational status. Women with lower education and those who were housewives had higher depression scores, consistent with evidence indicating that limited awareness, financial dependency, and reduced autonomy may increase vulnerability to PPD.

Interestingly, no significant association was found between mental health disorders and parity, gravida, or residence status, which differs from some local studies reporting higher psychological morbidity among multiparous women and rural residents. The lack of association in our study may reflect the relatively urbanized profile of the hospital's catchment population and uniform access to obstetric services. It also highlights that perinatal psychological distress can affect women irrespective of demographic factors and may be influenced more by psychosocial stressors than obstetric variables.

Overall, the findings reinforce the importance of integrating routine mental health screening with antenatal and postnatal care. Use of validated tools such as HADS and EPDS in outpatient settings can facilitate early detection and timely referral for psychological support. Given the high prevalence of mental health disorders demonstrated in this study, establishing structured counselling services, strengthening family involvement, and addressing socioeconomic barriers may substantially improve maternal well-being and overall pregnancy outcomes.

CONCLUSION:

The present study demonstrates a high frequency of mental health disorders among women during pregnancy and the postpartum period in a tertiary care setting in Hyderabad. Anxiety and antenatal depression were common during pregnancy, while postpartum depression affected a substantial proportion

of women following childbirth. These findings highlight the significant psychological burden experienced by women during the perinatal period, underscoring the need for routine mental health screening as part of standard antenatal and postnatal care. The study also identified key sociodemographic factors including maternal age, number of children, family income, educational status, and occupational status that influence the risk of developing anxiety and depressive disorders. Addressing these modifiable factors through counselling, improved social support, and accessible mental health services may reduce perinatal psychological morbidity. Integrating validated screening tools such as HADS and EPDS into routine maternal care and strengthening referral pathways for psychological support are crucial steps toward improving maternal well-being and overall pregnancy outcomes.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION:

Collection and acquisition of data & grammatical corrections	<i>Dr. Laila</i>
Concept & design of study & proof read	<i>Dr. Momna Khan</i>
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	<i>Dr. Baby Abida Parveen</i>
Revising critically and make it suitable for final format	<i>Dr. Komal</i>
Acquisition of data and grammatical review	<i>Dr. Sandhia</i>
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	<i>Dr. Versha</i>
Revision of the manuscript	<i>Dr. Labeeha Chaudhry</i>
Drafting the article	<i>Dr. Moiz Muhammad Shaikh</i>
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REFERENCES:

1. Kathree T, Selohilwe OM, Bhana A. Perceptions of postnatal depression and health care needs in a South African sample: the "mental" in maternal health care. *BMC Womens Health* 2014;14:140.
2. McCauley M, Brown A, Ofofu B, et al. "I just wish it becomes part of routine care": Healthcare providers' knowledge, attitudes and perceptions of screening for maternal mental health during and after pregnancy: a qualitative study. *BMC Psychiatry* 2019;19:304.

3. Gelaye B, Rondon MB, Araya R, et al.. Epidemiology of maternal depression, risk factors, and child outcomes in low-income and middle-income countries. *Lancet Psychiatry* 2016;3:973–82.
4. Atif N, Lovell K, Rahman A. Maternal mental health: The missing “m” in the global maternal and child health agenda. *Seminars in Perinatology* 2015;39:345–52.
5. Banti S, Mauri M, Oppo A. From the third month of pregnancy to 1 year postpartum. prevalence, incidence, recurrence, and new onset of depression: results from the perinatal depression–research and screening unit study. *Compr Psychiatry* 2011;52:343–51.
6. Biaggi A, Conroy S, Pawlby S. Identifying the women at risk of Antenatal anxiety and depression: a systematic review. *J Affect Disord* 2016;191:62–77.
7. Silva MMdeJ, Nogueira DA, Clapis MJ. Anxiety in pregnancy: prevalence and associated factors. *Rev Esc Enferm USP* 2017;51.
8. Ogbo FA, Eastwood J, Hendry A. Determinants of antenatal depression and postnatal depression in Australia. *BMC Psychiatry* 2018;18:1–11.
9. Lagadec N, Steinecker M, Kapassi A, Magnier AM, Chastang J, Robert S, et al. Factors influencing the quality of life of pregnant women: a systematic review. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2018;18(1):1–14.
10. Husain N, Cruickshank K, Husain M, Khan S, Tomenson B, Rahman A. Social stress and depression during pregnancy and in the postnatal period in British Pakistani mothers: a cohort study. *J Affect Disord*. 2012;140(3):268–76.
11. Watson H, Soltani H. Perinatal mental ill health: the experiences of women from ethnic minority groups. *Br J Midwifery*. 2019;27(10):642–48.
12. Jawed M, Pradhan NA, Mistry R, Nazir A, Shekhani S, Ali TS. Management of maternal depression: qualitative exploration of perceptions of healthcare professionals from a public tertiary care hospital, Karachi, Pakistan. *PLoS One*. 2021;16(7):e0254212.
13. Ali NS, Azam IS, Ali BS, Tabbusum G, Moin SS. Frequency and associated factors for anxiety and depression in pregnant women: a hospital-based cross-sectional study. *The Scientific World Journal*. 2012 Oct;2012.
14. Yadav T, Shams R, Khan AF, Azam H, Anwar M, Anwar T, Siddiqui C, Abbas K, Sukaina M 2nd, Ghazanfar S. Postpartum Depression: Prevalence and Associated Risk Factors Among Women in Sindh, Pakistan. *Cureus*. 2020 Dec 22;12(12):e12216.
15. Ali NS, Azam IS, Ali BS, Tabbusum G, Moin SS. Frequency and associated factors for anxiety and depression in pregnant women: A hospital-based cross-sectional study. *JPMA*. 2012;62(11):1209-12.
16. Haque A, Khan RA. Prevalence of perinatal anxiety in South Asian women: A systematic review. *Asian J Psychiatr*. 2021;58:102600.
17. Rahman A, Patel V, Maselko J, Kirkwood B. The neglected ‘m’ in maternal mental health: South Asian perspectives. *Lancet Psychiatry*. 2008;370(9598):864-70.
18. Dennis CL, Falah-Hassani K, Shiri R. Prevalence of antenatal and postnatal anxiety: Systematic review. *Br J Psychiatry*. 2017;210(5):315-23.
19. Kingston D, McDonald S, Austin MP, Tough S. Anxiety in pregnancy: Prevalence and risk factors. *J Affect Disord*. 2015;170:163-73.
20. Kazi A, Fatmi Z, Hatcher J, Kausar S, Khan A. Maternal depression and its impact on child health in Pakistan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2006;3(1):37-44.

21. Humayun A, Haider II, Imran N, Iqbal H. Antenatal depression and associated risk factors in Pakistan. *J Pak Psychiatr Soc.* 2013;10(2):31-4.
22. CDC. Depression during and after pregnancy. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. 2020.
23. Birhanu AM, Gebregziabher D, Belay YA. Prevalence and determinants of antenatal depression among pregnant women in Ethiopia. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2019;19:251.
24. Rahman A, Creed F. Postnatal depression and its risk factors in urban Pakistan. *Br J Psychiatry.* 2007;190:462-8.
25. Gulamani SS, Shaikh K, Kazmi T. Postpartum depression in Pakistan: A review. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2013;29(3):647-52.
26. Chandran M, Tharyan P, Muliylil J, Abraham S. Postpartum depression in a rural community in India. *Br J Psychiatry.* 2002;181:499-504.
27. O'Hara MW, McCabe JE. Postpartum depression: Current status and future directions. *Annu Rev Clin Psychol.* 2013;9:379-407.
28. Nasreen HE, Kabir ZN, Forsell Y, Edhborg M. Prevalence and determinants of antenatal depression in Bangladesh. *PLoS One.* 2011;6(7):e20773.
29. Patel V, Rahman A, Jacob KS, Hughes M. Effect of maternal mental health on infant growth in developing countries. *Lancet.* 2004;363(9401):833-9.

